

TYPES OF RECEIVED PRONUNCIATION

Mamatova Shakhribonu Badriddin qiziThe 3rd year BA student TSPU named after Nizami**Scientific advisor: Umarova Zaynura Tolibjon qizi**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7378099>

Abstract. *The accent that is historically considered as the most respectable and standard type of spoken British English is called Received Pronunciation (RP). This article entails the definition of RP, whether it is geographically neutral, the number of speakers, whether sub-varieties exist, how appropriate a choice it is as a standard, and how the accent has altered over time. In addition, the study of RP focuses solely on issues of pronunciation; vocabulary, grammar, and style, which are important to the study of language standards, are not taken into account.*

Keywords: *RP, pronunciation, orthoepic norm, conservative, contemporary, mainstream, local accent, regional standart, accent variation, dialect.*

ВИДЫ ПОЛУЧЕННОГО ПРОИЗНОШЕНИЯ

Аннотация. *Акцент, который исторически считается наиболее респектабельным и стандартным типом разговорного британского английского, называется Received Pronunciation (RP). Эта статья влечет за собой определение RP, независимо от того, является ли оно географически нейтральным, количество говорящих, существуют ли подразновидности, насколько это уместный выбор в качестве стандарта и как акцент изменился с течением времени. Кроме того, изучение RP сосредоточено исключительно на вопросах произношения; словарный запас, грамматика и стиль, важные для изучения языковых стандартов, не учитываются.*

Ключевые слова: *RP, произношение, орфоэпическая норма, консервативный, современный, мейнстрим, местный акцент, региональный стандарт, акцентная вариация, диалект.*

English became a universal language as a result of a variety of geographic, historical, and sociocultural factors. Dialect and accent are two fundamental characteristics that we separate according to geographic variance. A dialect can be identified by its vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. Therefore, there are two types of English: British and American.

Accent is a sort of pronunciation that can be targeted in either a person's or a group's speech. Vowels, consonants, word stress, rhythm, and intonation are social cues. The written and spoken languages are the two main varieties of language. Any spoken act that uses language as its medium is the outcome of a very intricate chain of circumstances. The spoken literary form has a uniform national pronunciation. "A socially accepted variety of a language established by a codified norm of correctness" is one definition of "standard." It is widely acknowledged that "Received Pronunciation" or RP. It's common to refer to a standard national pronunciation as a "orthoepic norm." However, some phoneticians favour the term "literary pronunciation." [1]

RP, or received pronunciation, is the instantly recognizable accent frequently referred to as "typically British" as the titles "the Queen's English," "Oxford English," and "BBC English," are frequently used to describe this accent. For instance, Queen Elizabeth II had an

almost singular accent, yet the English heard on the BBC or at Oxford University now has a variety of accents. All RP speakers use Standard English, hence RP is an accent rather than a dialect. In other words, they stay away from the localized vocabulary and grammatical constructs that are typical of regional dialects. Additionally, RP lacks any geographical specificity; that is, it offers no hints as to the speaker's origins. [5]

Even though RP is arguably the most researched and extensively documented variant of spoken English in the world, recent estimates indicate that only 3% of UK residents speak in it. In Scotland and Northern Ireland, it is hardly present, and it might be losing some of its respect in Wales. Therefore, an English accent is more appropriate to describe than a British one. RP is both a real accent and a theoretical idea in linguistics. It is the accent that dictionaries base their phonemic transcriptions on, and it is frequently taught as a second language to English students. As an example, adjectives like "mild" or "soft" are used to characterize speakers whose speech patterns are only slightly different from RP speakers, "wide" or "strong" regional accents are sometimes ascribed to individuals who utilize multiple more localized pronunciations. Therefore, we may say that one speaker has a strong Glaswegian accent while the other has a mild Scottish accent. Such descriptions are inadequate for Received Pronunciation, even if, like any English dialect, it includes a wide range of speakers.

Three general categories can be used to classify the different types of RP. . **Conservative RP** is a fairly traditional variation that is most often used by older speakers and members of the nobility. According to mainstream RP, an accent is one that conveys very few cues about the speaker's age, profession, or way of life. Modern RP refers to speakers who exhibit characteristics common to younger RP speakers. The fact that none of them employ any phonetic patterns that allow us to infer their place of origin in the UK, however, unites them all.

Conservative RP designates an older speaker's or aristocratic-sounding traditional accent. "High British" is another name for this. Although RP is not a regional accent, some counties' native accents are more similar to it than others. A person who attended a public school is typically identified by a strong RP accent.

Contemporary RP refers to speakers who use characteristics common to speakers of the younger generation, whereas **Mainstream RP** is an accent that is frequently considered neutral considering the age, employment, or lifestyle of the speaker. Today, there is almost any distinction between those two. [6]

The accents are associated with the people who use them, with their way of life. The accents of major cities in the UK, such as Liverpool, Birmingham, and Glasgow, may be associated negatively with the polluted surroundings of industrial areas. An RP speaker is typically thought to have traits like authority, competence, intelligence, and ambition, whereas a local accent is linked to friendliness, integrity, and kindness.

Regarding accents, they relate to the differences in pronunciation that reveal a person's country of origin. Social mobility and new settlement patterns help to partially explain these variants. Different groups or social formations within the total can be distinguished from one another in a number of ways, including by gender, age, class, and ethnicity. Particular groups will often have distinctive methods of speaking the language, and these will serve as markers for the separation of one group from another

Numerous studies have demonstrated the significance of age, sex, and socioeconomic status in explaining the variations in accents:

-RP – 3-5% upper class

-Regional standard – 55% middle-middle class, low-middle class

-Local accent – 40% upper-working class, middle-working class, low-middle class

To sum up, Received Pronunciation (RP) is the proper term to describe the regionally neutral accent used by many middle-class speakers in the UK, particularly in England. It is frequently used as a lexical reference point and as a guide when teaching English to speakers of other languages. It is well known and frequently used as a model for teaching English as a second language, as well as the foundation for dictionaries'.

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